

[JPI HDHL "FOODRETEC"] - Committed to the responsible development of meat replacement products and practices (ComMEATted)

Petrescu-Mag, R. M., Pistea, I., Ginsca, C., Cuius, L., & Petrescu, D. C. (2024). Meat Replacers in Romania: Preliminary Findings in a Nutshell. Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. CNCS/CCCDI-UEFISCDI, project number ERANET-JPI-HDHL-ComMEATted, within PNCDI IV.

MEAT REPLACERS IN ROMANIA: PRELIMINARY FINDINGS IN A NUTSHELL

The project “Committed to the responsible development of meat replacement products and practices: comparing multidimensional barriers and potentials in European countries” examines, from an interdisciplinary perspective and across five countries (France, Ireland, Norway, Austria, and Romania), how a dietary transition toward reduced meat consumption can be possible and under what conditions.

The project explores the sustainable transition toward the production, distribution, and responsible consumption of meat replacers. Traditional dietary habits and cultural norms vary significantly in Europe, creating a complex landscape for the introduction of alternative proteins. Therefore, the project proposes an innovative approach that integrates various contextual factors, including social, cultural, legislative, economic, psychological, ethical, and ideological considerations.

The objective of the project is to facilitate the responsible development of alternative proteins (considering three products – insect-based, plant-based, and synthetic meat) in Europe, contributing to the creation of a sustainable, diversified, and innovative food system that involves multiple stakeholders. The project aims to answer a key question: “What factors influence consumers and other European stakeholders to adopt diets that include alternative proteins, such as synthetic meat, plant-based products and insect-based products?”

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS FROM ROMANIA

ROMANIA 	20 in-depth interviews	July-October 2024	Occupational fields: farmers, religious organizations, animal welfare associations, athletes, influencers, representatives of the HORECA sector, researchers.
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Economic factors:

- Policies and economic measures are needed to support meat replacers, such as subsidies, public funding, research support, and environmental taxes;
- The challenges of high production costs and limited market access are highlighted.

Social-cultural factors:

- Familiarity with meat replacers: meat replacers are mainly associated with plant-based products;
- There is a cultural attachment to “conventional” meat;
- Importance of nutritional content, especially protein, in shaping consumer perceptions;
- Potential opportunities to create a new food culture in urban areas that are open to innovative foods.

Ethical and justice considerations:

- Concerns about the health implications of processed meat replacers, including additives and preservatives;
- Concerns about the social impact on small producers and rural communities;
- Concerns about corruption and lobbying in the meat replacer industry.

Environmental impact:

- There is a perceived positive environmental contribution of meat replacers, such as reducing carbon footprints and pollution;
- Skepticism about long-term sustainability and the potential unforeseen environmental impacts is observed.

OBSTACLES

High production costs, market accessibility; Limited financial incentives; Cultural resistance; Lack of familiarity; Perception of nutritional inadequacy; Psychological barriers, due to negative perceptions about taste or the idea of eating something unnatural (for insect-based or synthetic meat), and fear of the unknown (new food technologies and unfamiliar ingredients); Health concerns; Perceived negative impact on small producers; Unforeseen environmental impacts such as potential risks associated with waste management, emissions, and other negative effects that lack transparent information.

MOTIVATIONS

Reduction of carbon footprint; Sustainability goals; Animal welfare; Healthier diet options.

SOLUTIONS

Economic incentives and policy support; Enhanced public awareness; Transparent labeling and regulation; Changes in terminology.